

Indian Knowledge System for Well-being of Elite Athletes: A Case Study

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This study introduces a multimodal M⁴ model of mental wellness - grounded in indigenous therapies and practices from Indian Knowledge System (IKS), designed to provide rapid relief for transient mental health concerns in elite athletes. The model integrates empirically supported mind- body contemplative techniques to proactively address acute sleep deprivation, pre-competition stress, anxiety, and emotional reactivity. The M⁴ interventions were implemented with an Olympian gymnast experiencing short term sleep disturbance and heightened anxiety before an international competition. Intervention efficacy was evaluated using a structured, time-staggered approach. Findings indicate promising benefits in sleep onset, emotional regulation, emotional stability and training quality. These results position the M⁴ model as a culturally grounded, practice based bridge between indigenous knowledge and contemporary sport psychology. Further systematic validation and cross cultural replication of the model are recommended.

Keywords: Mental health, mental well-being in sports, mental well-being training model, indigenous methods

Elite athletes frequently experience mental health challenges that manifest uniquely within the sporting context (Rice et al., 2016) and may hinder performance. Simon Biles, the Olympic gymnast shook the sporting world on July 28, 2021 by withdrawing from the Tokyo Olympics Games (2021) citing the need to protect her mental health. The International Olympic Committee subsequently implemented comprehensive mental-health initiatives ahead of the 2024 Summer Olympics, highlighting the increasing recognition that psychological well-being is essential for sustained performance excellence (IOC, 2024).

They encounter both clinical and transient psychological challenges, such as anxiety, overthinking, restlessness, emotional reactivity, and sleep disruption (Grandner et al., 2021). While structured long-term interventions exist for clinical conditions, athletes often require immediate support for acute, situational stressors arising before or during competition. These high-pressure contexts create a need for brief, accessible “SOS” interventions that provide rapid relief while remaining sensitive to performance demands.

In many cultural contexts, including India, stigma surrounding mental health further complicates help-seeking. Athletes may delay psychological consultation due to concerns about reputation, team selection, or perceived weakness. Consequently, sport psychologists are frequently approached as a last-minute resource, with

expectations of immediate solutions for both acute and longstanding concerns. This pattern underscores a significant gap in addressing short-term psychological needs within high-performance environments.

To meet this need, sport psychology practice must expand beyond standardized approaches and incorporate innovative, culturally grounded interventions. Just as medical treatment requires individualized prescriptions, psychological interventions must be tailored to the athlete's context, culture, and presenting concern. Indigenous knowledge systems offer time-tested practices that address mindbody regulation and holistic well-being. Integrating such culturally congruent methods into applied sport psychology may enhance accessibility, acceptability, and immediacy of care, particularly for transient mental wellness challenges that do not require clinical treatment. To illustrate the application of such a culturally grounded SOS intervention, the following case describes an elite athlete who presented with acute mental wellness concerns in a high-performance context.

The Participant Background and her Mental Health Issues

The participant is a 28 years old, an Olympian artistic gymnast and represented the country in the Olympics, World Cup, Commonwealth Games, and Asian Championship. She is a medallist in vault in an international championship.

Two days before leaving for an international championship, she was referred to me by her coach. During our telephonic conversation, she reported being unable to sleep for two consecutive nights, staying awake throughout both nights. On the third day, she developed a headache, pain and cramps in the legs. She described feeling disturbed, emotionally reactive and increasingly anxious as competition time drew closer. She also noted herself overreacting to minor situations, and crying often, which was otherwise quite unlike her. She confessed to being over-emotional and found herself crying even when she saw a friend in distress. This combination of stress, sleep deprivation and personal worries had started affecting her performance during practice. Her coach also expressed concern

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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emphasising the urgency of addressing her well-being, as they were flying out after two days for a major international competition that was scheduled 10 days away.

Some of her mental worries appeared to stem from personal issues, shared during our conversation with her. These problems intensified as she found herself caught between her personal responsibilities and the pressure of the upcoming competition. The intervention was delivered in two sessions the following day, complemented by guided self-practice.

The Intervention: M⁴-Massage, Music, Mind Yoga, and Meditation

A multimodal therapeutic approach was necessary to address the athlete's concerns within the limited time available. The M⁴ intervention-Massage, Music, Mind Yoga and Meditation was designed, as a layered self-regulation intervention targeting physiological, attentional, cognitive, and emotional systems.

Rooted in Indian indigenous knowledge systems, these practices are widely recognized for promoting calmness, reducing stress, and restoring sleep. Conceptually, the M⁴ model aligns with principles of Solution-Focused Therapy by directing attention toward cultivating desired psychological states rather than analysing dysfunction. Each component was sequenced to facilitate small but meaningful regulatory shifts, positioning the athlete as an active agent through structured self-practice. The intervention structure is detailed below.

Massage

Massage was introduced as the first component to induce rapid physiological downregulation. Head and foot massage are deeply embedded in Indian daily practice. Empirical evidence indicates these techniques have been associated with parasympathetic activation and reductions in sympathetic arousal, enhance oxygen flow to the brain, lower heart rate, regulate breathing, and reduce perceived stress (Fenwick, 2015; Howard & Halldorsson, 2013; Hayes & Cox, 1999; Jong et al., 2000; Lee & Yeun, 2017). Given the athlete's heightened pre-competition arousal and sleep disturbance, massage served as an entry point to restore autonomic balance.

Mind Yoga

A brief discourse on *Samatvam Yog Uchyate* (Verse 2.48) meaning "Equanimity is yoga," from the Srimad Bhagavad Gita, was incorporated as the mental and spiritual wellness practice. *Samatvam* (equanimity), a mental yogic practice, is a key psychological factor that enhances mental well-being by reducing emotional reactivity, improving mental health outcomes, and demonstrating therapeutic potential (Desbordes et al., 2014; Eberth et al., 2019; Jijina & Biswas, 2021; Weber, 2021).

According to the Srimad Bhagavad Gita, equanimity is the evenness of mind in all circumstances-adversity, pleasure, or pain. Principles of *Samatvam* emphasise: 1) remaining objective to all experiences to maintain mental calmness in all circumstances (Verse 6.8, 12.13-14, 14.24-25); 2) *Karma Yoga* (Verse 2:47)-commitment to performance of duties without worrying for the outcome; 3) controlling reactivity by regulating emotions and understanding impermanence or transitory nature of all experiences (verse 2:14). Within the M⁴ framework, *Samatvam* functioned as a cognitive reappraisal strategy, encouraging non-reactivity, task focus, and outcome detachment consistent with performance psychology

principles.

Music

Music was incorporated as the third component of the M⁴ intervention to facilitate emotional regulation and physiological calming. The therapeutic effects of music in promoting emotional release, reducing stress, restlessness, and anxiety are well established (Sachs et al., 2015; De Witte et al., 2020). Meditative music, in particular, has demonstrated calming effects and reductions in pre-procedural stress in clinical contexts (Lee et al., 2017).

Flute-based music was intentionally selected due to its soft tonal quality, sustained breath-generated sound, and established use in music therapy practice (Hadar & Amir, 2018). Survey research involving professional music therapists indicates that the flute is commonly incorporated into therapeutic settings, reflecting its perceived suitability for relaxation and emotional modulation (Burns, 2019). Additionally, flute music has been associated with cognitive and affective benefits (Laksmidewi et al., 2019).

Within the present intervention, a flute-based meditative audio track was paired with *Yog Nidra* to enhance immersion, promote parasympathetic activation, and support emotional settling. The choice of flute music was therefore guided by both empirical support and its compatibility with the broader self-regulation objectives of the M⁴ model.

Meditation

Pranayama and *Yog Nidra* (*YN*) meditation methods were introduced for relaxation and restoring sleep. *Pranayama*, the Indian yogic breathing meditation method-involves deep, slow alternate nostril inhalation and exhalation. *Pranayama* has reported benefits in the improvement of restorative sleep and sleep disorders quality (Jagadeesan, 2022; Onder, 2019), calm and relax the mind and decrease perceived stress (Hepburn & McMahon, 2017).

Yog Nidra (*YN*), an ancient Indian 'yogic sleep' or 'psychic sleep' meditative method, which has empirical validation for sleeplessness and stress reduction (Dwivedi, 2021). Neuroimaging studies confirm that *YN* produces measurable effects on the central nervous system (CNS) and reduces mild anxiety on psychometric indices (Pandi-Perumal et al., 2022). A brief duration *YN* meditation (11-minute daily for 30 days) positively influenced stress reduction, sleep onset, sleep quality, mindfulness, and overall well-being across heterogeneous populations (Datta et al., 2017; Moszeik et al., 2020). *YN* improved sleep quality in two karate elite athletes (Fronso et al., 2024) yet its application as an intervention for sleep, relaxation, and overall well-being remains unexplored in sports. Within the M⁴ sequence, *Pranayama* and *YN* consolidated the physiological and cognitive shifts initiated by the preceding components, facilitating deeper relaxation and sleep restoration.

Intervention Application Method

All four interventions were applied across two sessions of 45-60 minutes each: first in-person session, and second online video session on *YN* at the client's bed time. Each intervention targeted distinct therapeutic effects and, collectively, contributed to overall well-being as outlined earlier.

Session 1

The first session began with psychoeducation, during which we

discussed the intervention design and its therapeutic benefits with the client. After obtaining her commitment to self-practice, the first session formally commenced with a therapeutic head massage administered by her professional masseuse. She received a full head massage with gentle relaxation of pressure points for approximately 5 to 6 minutes. This was followed by a 5-minute foot massage using circular motion, particularly focussing on the soles and toes stretching. She was advised to incorporate foot massage into her bedtime routine.

Following the massage therapy session, after a brief break, a discourse on the three principles of *Samatvam* (equanimity), as detailed in model outline, was delivered to explain both its meaning and practical application. The athlete was encouraged to contemplate uncontrollable factors so that she could sharpen her focus on inner controllable factors. The exercise sought to foster mental calmness, direct inward focus towards controllable factors, and minimize distractions. The athlete was encouraged to internalise these principles over the subsequent days through reflective contemplation and mental conditioning, to cultivate equanimity as a stable, enduring mindset expressed in embodied action.

The discourse session was followed by a guided practice of *Pranayama* (*Anulom Vilom* or alternate nostril breathing) for 5-6 minutes to help her experience the immediate sense of relief it provides. She was advised to practice it twice daily, and additionally whenever she felt overwhelmed or stressed, for 10 minutes each day until the competition and beyond.

Session 2

The second online video session on *YN* was conducted at bedtime with the participant following the guided instructions provided by the researcher. *YN* is a complete relaxation technique performed in a *Shavasana* (lying corpse posture). *YN* guided meditation involves relaxing each part of the body in a systematic manner, turning inward attention. After initial relaxation of body parts, a *Sankalp* (resolution) is taken and chanted in the mind a number of times, and repeated at the end of the session. *Sankalp* (resolution) is a short sentence that is repeated in the mind for cognitive restructuring. We used "I am sleeping" as the *Sankalp*. The *Sankalp* method was adapted in two ways: i) instead of repeating the command in the beginning and at the end of the process we repeated the *Sankalp* during the entire process, ii) adding the duration of sleep and gradually increasing it in the *Sankalp* statement. The *Sankalp* that we used was: "I am sleeping for the last 5 minutes," gradually increasing to "I am sleeping for 3 hours," repeating each command three times. A *YN* video link is shared for the readers. <https://www.youtube.com/live/RcXemRLVW1Q?si=NswjMEjJD8UFdetY>

She was advised to pair flute music audio with the guided *YN* meditation during the session. Within 30-35 minutes of the session, she reported feeling sleepy, and the session was subsequently concluded. Subsequently, she was instructed to continue listening to the *YN* audio at bedtime for as many days as she deemed necessary.

This represents my second case study employing *Pranayama* and *YN* meditation, building on the positive outcomes observed in the first case with a swimmer. In this case, the intervention was associated with improved sleep quality, increased sleep duration, and enhanced relaxation, as indicated by objective assessments. However, these findings remain unpublished and should therefore be interpreted cautiously.

Evaluation

The evaluation of the M^4 intervention was conducted using a practice-based, multi-informant approach. Data were collected through (a) immediate participant feedback, (b) coach observations, and (c) a semi-structured follow-up interview conducted 10 days post-competition. Although no standardized pre and post-psychometric measures were administered due to lack of time, this time-staggered and multi-source evaluation allowed for preliminary triangulation of perceived short-term outcomes across sleep, emotional regulation, and training engagement.

The participant provided qualitative feedback the next morning through a recorded voice message. She expressed gratitude and shared that she was able to fall asleep within 30 minutes of the *YN* intervention and experienced uninterrupted sleep for approximately 7 hours. Her words are quoted below:

Yesterday, after you hung up the call, I went to sleep after 30 minutes. And I woke up at 6 in the morning, maybe 5 o'clock, 6 o'clock maybe. I had kept my phone a little far away, so I didn't see the time. And I fell asleep yesterday.

This account indicates a clear improvement in sleep onset and continuity, which was a key goal of the intervention. Further supporting this, her coach reported an observable improvement in her practice performance the following day, indicating a transfer of sleep and relaxation benefits to athletic function. Additionally, she also reported a positive shift in focus, energy, and overall training quality during the training session.

To assess the sustainability and real-world integration of the M^4 intervention, a follow-up evaluation was conducted 10 days after the athlete returned from the championship, where she bagged a bronze medal. This provided an opportunity to explore not only performance outcomes but also the ongoing applicability of the intervention during a high-pressure, competitive context. During the follow-up, the athlete reported that she had routinely incorporated two techniques-foot massage and meditative flute audio-into her nightly routine. She reported continued reflection on the principles of *Samatvam* (mental yoga) with the intention of internalising them into embodied action. Additionally, she also continued practicing *Pranayama* once daily. These minimal yet consistent practices helped her feel calm and relaxed, thereby contributing to restful sleep. Collectively, the multi-source feedback indicates promising effects of the M^4 interventions, while highlighting the need for further systematic evaluations.

Discussion

The M^4 intervention, demonstrated encouraging outcomes when applied both as an SOS (emergency) strategy and as a proactive measure. The findings suggest that culturally grounded methods may provide simple, accessible, and adaptable relief for acute mental wellness concerns in athletes. Evaluation feedback highlights the M^4 model's flexibility, allowing athletes to tailor its components according to personal and contextual demands, while requiring minimal resources and promoting proactive self-management of well-being.

Drawing from indigenous knowledge systems, these approaches offer complementary strategies for addressing transient mental wellness issues that do not require clinical intervention. However, the athlete's championship performance cannot be attributed to the intervention, as performance enhancement was not the intended

objective. Further empirical research is required before definitive conclusions can be drawn.

Conclusion and Applied Implications of the Study

The present study highlights the potential value of integrating culturally grounded, proactive mind-body interventions into sport psychology practice. For practitioners, the findings support expanding the therapeutic toolkit beyond conventional cognitive-behavioural or Western-centric models, thereby enhancing practitioner competence across diverse modalities. Such interventions can be seamlessly embedded within training schedules or pre-competition routines, providing a practical, adaptable option. Aligning well-being strategies with athletes' cultural contexts and belief systems, may enhance receptivity and effectiveness. Within the holistic athlete management framework, such proactive practices can support transient stress recovery, emotional regulation, improved sleep quality, and the management of pre-performance worries. When applied thoughtfully within evidence-based frameworks, openness to non-Western approaches allows for more individualized and comprehensive support—particularly in multicultural sport environments—provided practitioners maintain cultural sensitivity and contextual awareness.

Limitations of the Study

A key limitation of this study is the short follow-up duration and the M¹ intervention outcomes are limited to a single case. Although single case studies are powerful ways to bridge the gap between theory and practice (Rabu & Binder, 2025) and useful in disseminating underrepresented time tested indigenous practices across communities of the world.

Future Directions

Future studies should systematically evaluate the individual and combined effects of the indigenous interventions employed in the study using controlled experimental designs, larger sample sizes, and diverse athlete populations for robust outcome measures. Longitudinal research is needed to examine their sustained impact on mental well-being through extended follow-up periods. Additionally, cross cultural comparisons may help identify differences in acceptance and effectiveness, thereby informing global sport psychology practices. The development of culturally sensitive and objective assessment tools is essential to enhance generalizability and scientific rigor. Furthermore, advancing practitioner training models that build competencies in culturally adaptive interventions is strongly recommended.

Data Availability Statement

Data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the corresponding author. Data are not publicly available due to privacy and ethical concerns.

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Received February 18, 2026
Revision received March 8, 2026
Accepted March 10, 2026